

ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИНИ ЎҚИТИШДА КОММУНИКАТИВ ЁНДАШУВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Бугунги кунда замонавий жамиятлар ҳаётнинг ижтимоий, иқтисодий ва сиёсий жиҳатларига таъсир кўрсатадиган тез ва чуқур ўзгаришлар ва кескинликларга дуч келмоқдалар. Таълимнинг роли ҳам минг йиллик даврда ўзгара бошлади. Дарҳақиқат, 21-аср таълими талабалар ўқув муҳитида ривожланиши керак бўлган турли хил ваколатларни ҳисобга олган ҳолда ўқув режаси тузилишини босқичма-босқич ўзгартиришни талаб қилади. Замонавий билимга асосланган тил таълими, талабалар олиши керак бўлган кўникма ва малакалар турлари ўтмишда ишлатилганидан фарқ қилади. Коммуникатив компетенция тил таълимининг энг муҳим жиҳатларидан биридир. Инглиз тилини ўқитишда коммуникатив ёндашувни жорий этиши ўқитилаётган тил кўникмаларининг мумкин бўлишига ёрдам беради ўз эҳтиёжлари, қизиқишлари ва имкониятларидан келиб чиқиб, ўз мамлакатидан ташқарида фойдаланиши.

Калит сўзлар: *коммуникатив методология, алоқа, тил ўрганиши, функционалик, амалий билим, коммуникатив компетенция, коммуникатив ёндашув, ижтимоий тил, вазифаларга асосланган тил ўрганиши, матнга асосланган ўқитиши.*

КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Сегодня современные общества все чаще сталкиваются с быстрыми и глубокими изменениями и напряженностью, которые затрагивают социальные, экономические и политические аспекты жизни. Роль образования также стала меняться в тысячелетнюю эпоху. На самом деле, образование 21-го века требует постепенного изменения структуры учебного плана с учетом различных компетенций, которые студенты должны развивать в условиях обучения. Современное языковое образование, основанное на знаниях, типы навыков и компетенций, которые должны получить обучаемые, отличаются от тех, что использовались в прошлом. Коммуникативная компетентность является одним из наиболее важных аспектов в языковом образовании. Внедрение коммуникативного подхода в преподавание английского языка способствует тому, что обучаемые языковые навыки могут

использоваться за пределами своей страны на основе собственных потребностей, интересов и возможностей.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативная методология, коммуникация, изучение языка, функциональность, практические знания, коммуникативная компетентность, коммуникативный подход, социальный язык, изучение языка на основе задач, текстовое обучение.

COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

A communicative technique today is undoubtedly the most effective way to learn English. It appeared abroad around the 60s of the last century, and came to our country around the mid-90s. The communicative technique is focused on the possibility of communication. Of the four "whales" on which any language training (reading, writing, speaking and perception of speech by ear) rests, increased attention is paid to the last two. The communicative method is designed primarily to relieve fear of communication. Communication is manifested in the functionality of training. Functionality assumes that both words and grammatical forms are absorbed immediately in the activity, based on its implementation.

Keywords: *communicative methodology, communication, language learning, functionality, practical knowledge, communicative competence, communicative approach, social language, task-based language learning, text-based teaching.*

Introduction

Like any method of learning a foreign language, the communicative method has its drawbacks, but together with the methodologists of our school we managed to correct them, which contributed to improving the effectiveness of our classes, as well as increased the results of our students. The main disadvantage is that it is quite difficult for a beginner to learn a foreign language to delve into the difficult grammatical basics

presented immediately in a foreign language, which is why education in our school is gradually from simple to complex. In addition, the following disadvantages can be identified: 1. "Complete abandonment of the native language, which is mandatory for communicative teaching methods, can cause stress for untrained students." For this, the teachers of the Star Talk school gradually introduce their students into the language environment, at the first lessons explanations are made in their native language, as they get used to it, the teacher completely switches to a foreign language. As you know, the goal of teaching a foreign language is practical language proficiency, assimilation of the language system and the acquisition of language skills. However, experience shows that often after graduation, even the best students do not have the skills of spontaneous speech, their poor vocabulary and the same type of design of grammatical structures are felt. Specially conducted studies have shown that more than 90% of training sessions in a foreign language are mainly aimed at teaching the language system, and not at mastering it. The main subject and object of training under the traditional method is the teacher. He directs speech activities, gives comments and organizes the training process as a whole: [1; 15-16-page]). At the same time, teaching methods and techniques are not aimed at the formation and development of speech skills and skills of students. The traditional method of learning English is also called grammar-translation. It consists in a systematic study of grammatical material, phonetics, and forms translation and reading skills. Students make dialogues, memorize them, teach words on topics, retell texts, perform written grammatical exercises.

Methods

The main features of this approach are memorizing the material and being thorough. A feature of the traditional methodology is that in the process of work, students must master all types of speech activities in a given volume. Currently, the so-called communicative method of mastering the language is also widely used. A communicative approach to language learning (communicative approach) is not a new technique at all: it appeared abroad around the 60s of the last century, and came to our country around the mid-90s [1; 23-24-pp.]) and they cannot speak. Adherents of a

communicative approach took the path of combating this discrepancy. Since then, the communicative technique has changed significantly and has become widespread around the world. She originally envisioned group classes with a native speaker. From the very first lesson, the training was conducted in English. The approach later underwent some changes and is now used in both the group and individual sessions. Much has been said and written about its effectiveness. The results are achieved by minimizing the use of the native language of the student during classes. With this approach, it is very important to teach a person to think in a foreign language so that he perceives foreign speech without any associations with his native language. With this teaching method, the study of theoretical moments is minimized or absent at all, and the main attention is paid to live communication, that is, spoken language. Discussion of real life situations attracts students, arouses keen interest and a desire to share their ideas. The main place in communicative learning of a foreign language is occupied by game situations, working with a partner, tasks for finding errors that not only allow you to increase the lexical stock, but also teach you to think analytically. Many advocates of a communicative approach support the use of authentic materials in the class. These can be different language realities, such as magazines, advertisements and newspapers, or visual sources around which communication can be built (maps, graphs, tables, etc.). The main task of the communicative technique is to help the student get rid of the notorious language barrier. About 70% of the communication method class is devoted to conversational practice on various topics. And yet it would be a mistake to assume that communicative approach is exclusively English language conversations. The communicative approach is designed to develop oral and written speech, vocabulary, grammar, listening and reading skills. The teacher goes through three stages of training with the student: engagement (involvement), study (study) and activation (activation - use). At the engagement stage, the teacher involves the student in the learning process: initiates an exciting discussion, offers to discuss the picture, problem, film, etc. [1; 51-52-page]). At the stage of study, the student is explained the grammatical theme and the use of new words and expressions,

that is, they are working on expanding the vocabulary and mastering grammar. At the knowledge activation stage, the student performs various exercises to consolidate the new grammar and words. This may be a continuation of the discussion of the topic under study, but already using the knowledge gained.

Results and Discussion

Like any other way of learning the language, the communicative approach has transformed over time, yet its founding principles have not changed. These include the following: 1. The student begins to speak English from the first lesson. Even those who learn the language from scratch master a couple dozen phrases in the first lesson. This allows you to quickly get used to the sound of speech, warns the appearance of a language barrier or gets rid of it. 2. When learning a language using this method, you do not need to choose whether to speak freely or speak correctly. The challenge is to make speech fluent and literate at the same time. Modern authentic aids are used in training. Carefully developed English-language texts contain fascinating practical material that can be used in life and in professional activities. The ability to speak competently is the main skill that a communicative technique is working to improve. Students are taught not only to talk about different topics, but also to monitor the correctness of speech. It is no secret that the language barrier often develops from the fact that a person is afraid to make a mistake in a conversation. And this fear is successfully fought by a communicative approach: up to 70% of the lesson time is devoted to the development of the speaking skill. Communicative approach helps to remove both the language and psychological barriers directly: students lose their fear of talking in English. The more and more often the student speaks English, the faster he learns to formulate his thoughts. And in classes using a communicative technique, students talk most of the lesson. The teacher builds a dialogue in such a way that students are interested in answering questions and they can use the knowledge gained to the maximum. [2; 11-13-page]). The communicative method teaches coherent speech, various colloquial phrases and clichés that allow later fluent speech. Students learn not only to hear, but also to understand English speech. In the classes, students

listen to and disassemble small audio and video materials with the teacher. Usually such material is used as a basis for discussion. The communicative method of teaching English is aimed at developing the ability to spontaneously speak on various topics. The classes use mainly only the language they learn. The teacher sometimes explains complex nuances in Russian, but 90% of the lesson is held in English. This technique allows not only to "rebuild" to use the English language, but also to stop mentally translating Russian phrases into English and vice versa. Grammar and vocabulary are studied for communication, not "for show." The communicative technique assumes a very correct and simple principle of studying grammatical constructions: no one shakes the theory. The teacher explains this or that rule and, together with students, begins to work it out in practice, bringing the skill of its use to automatism. They do the same with new words: no cramming, only repeated practical use. Recently, it has become fashionable to talk about how children learn their native language in order to try to copy this process when learning a foreign language. Remember how children learn the language: they speak first, and already in the process of communication, adults explain to them how to speak correctly. So, if you ask any of us how a child learns the pronunciation, phonetics of his language, then most of us will say: imitating parents. Children, unlike us, talk, even having a meager vocabulary and having no idea about grammar, are not afraid to make a mistake and do not judge themselves for mistakes made. The lack of complexes helps children immerse themselves in a foreign language without unnecessary baggage. The communicative approach is applied in much the same way: students discuss an interesting topic and learn to apply a new construction or vocabulary during the conversation. For example, the teacher explains the second type of conditional offers and offers to talk about dreams: If I won much money, I would buy a Ferrari (If I had won a lot of money, I would have bought a Ferrari). After 5-10 sentences, students easily memorize this construction and understand the principles of its use. That is, grammar and vocabulary are not actually the main subject of study, but are used as auxiliary material and learn automatically. Life does not stand still, and the communicative technique continues to develop. So, they began to use it

in an individual form of education and in online lessons. Moreover, the communicative approach in English classes on Skype has its own distinctive features. 1. Individual approach. An individual approach means that the teacher adapts the training program to a specific student. After all, people differ from each other both in natural properties (abilities), and in the ability to carry out educational and speech activities, and in their characteristics as a person: personal experience, the context of the activity, a set of certain feelings and emotions, interests, status (position) in the team [2; 27-28-page]). In English classes on Skype according to a communicative method, all the teacher's attention is focused on only one student. This allows you to detect gaps in knowledge and quickly eliminate them. Thus, the student will not be too easy or too difficult in the lesson, he will have an incentive to develop, and at the same time he will thoroughly understand all the topics studied. 2. Choosing the scope and type of homework for students. It is worth noting that homework should not be completely abandoned, since homework is the best way to fix material in memory and check how well it is learned. Homework in a communicative sub-27th course is never boring - it can be online tests and crosswords, songs and various resources in English to test knowledge. 3. Using grammar and vocabulary as an auxiliary material and learning them automatically. As in ordinary, classroom classes, in online classes, students do not teach dry wording of the rules. They learn the natural use of grammatical constructs and really useful words and expressions in practice. 4. Maximum practice in class. For most of the class, students exercise in speaking. A few minutes are devoted to reading an interesting text, which later becomes a topic for discussion. Tasks for improving writing and listening skills are most often given at home. So, you can listen to the text or write a letter, taking your time, in a calm atmosphere. If something is not clear, the teacher will definitely come to the rescue and explain everything in the lesson. This approach allows you to save time and engage in the development of colloquial speech, because this skill, as a rule, is mastered the hardest. [3; 39-40-page]). This solves the problem described at the beginning of the article: "I understand everything, but I cannot speak." The communicative technique, despite the lack of "novelty" and "innovative approach," has

many advantages. To date, this is undoubtedly the most effective way to learn English. Thus, we can say with confidence: the communicative method of teaching English is suitable for absolutely everyone, and it will be especially appreciated by those who have not had a very pleasant experience of learning the language in ancient textbooks.

Conclusion

The communicative technique is focused on the possibility of communication. Of the four "whales" on which any language training (reading, writing, speaking and perception of speech by ear) rests, increased attention is paid to the last two. The communicative method is designed primarily to relieve fear of communication. Communication is manifested in the functionality of training. Functionality assumes that both words and grammatical forms are absorbed immediately in the activity, based on its implementation. Based on the above, it can be concluded that communicativity is necessary in the learning process, since it serves to ensure that communication occurs in adequate conditions, such as taking into account the personality of each student, the speech orientation of the learning process, the functionality of training, situational communication, and the constant novelty of the learning process.

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